

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: In this article, innovative methods of teaching English are considered as creative, which transform the nature of learning in relation to such properties as target orientation, the nature of interaction between teachers and pupils, their positions during training, create a favorable atmosphere in the classroom.

Keywords: *innovative methods, self-realization, reproductive nature, group work, creative activity*

The purpose of introducing innovative methods of teaching English into the educational process is not just the accumulation of knowledge and skills, but the constant enrichment of creative experience, the formation of a mechanism for self-organization and self-realization of each pupil, increasing his educational motivation. There is a variety of innovative methods of teaching a foreign language in the methodology. In order to ensure a complete understanding of lexical and grammatical material at the stage of skill formation, repeated joint implementation of actions for its assimilation and constant reinforcement and monitoring of the correctness of these actions by the teacher, it is advisable to use teamwork. Here, I will share some sample of team-work techniques which can be implemented in English lessons.

Think-Pair-Share structure (think, discuss in a couple, then in a group of four people and share your thoughts with the class). The teacher names a situation and a speech task of a transformational or reproductive nature and pronounces a sentence.

Step 1. The members of the group individually think about the answer.

Step 2. The pupil reports the answer to the partner in the pair, and together they say a common answer.

Step 3. Pupils share information with each other in a group, compose an answer and choose a pupil who voices it.

This type of work is interesting to pupils, as there is a moment of competition. Pupils in the group strive to come to a consensus as soon as possible. In addition, this type of work contributes to the cohesion of the group.

Another technique is called as Fact or fiction and guess the fib. This method assumes a speech task of a wildcard or reproductive nature. Solving it, individual members of the group take turns pronouncing sentences. Those who listen are trying to determine whether the sentences correspond to reality. (If they match, then the sentences are repeated.) If the sentences do not correspond to reality, each pupil utters 2-3 sentences. One of them contradicts reality. This is exactly what the members of the group repeat. At the stage of skills improvement, it is advisable to introduce group forms of work. Group work is a methodical technique related to a group of active ways of teaching practical knowledge of English. The introduction of this technique into the educational process contributes to the achievement of the goals of teaching dialogic speech, monologue, monologue utterance, the development of creative activity, the formation of pupils' skills and abilities of independent expression of thought, education and upbringing of pupils by means of a foreign language. There is a wide variety of forms of group work. I will consider those that, in our opinion, are the most interesting and whose effectiveness we have tested in practice. A sample of group-work is Buzz groups where pupils form small groups, turning to their neighbors, in order to discuss the issue (within 2-3 minutes). The teacher controls the work of pupils, moving from one group to another. After a brief discussion, the representative of the group reports the general decision to the whole group. I managed to test this form of work when working on the topic "How many friends have you got?" Pupils actively answered the teacher's questions based on the text they read, gave complete and accurate answers, which suggests that this work stimulates their cognitive activity, increases interest in the subject.

Another method is named as panels where pupils selected by the teacher (usually advanced pupils) sit down in front of the group of interviewees. The rest of the group - correspondents ask them questions that need to be answered. Such a discussion can be held on the basis of the read text, during which to discuss the plot, characters, etc. This form of group work requires preliminary preparation of interviewees and reference cards, schemes for "correspondents" that will help support the logic of the discussion. The panel provides an opportunity for advanced pupils to show their knowledge, and for weaker pupils to develop auditory abilities. I used this form of group work on the topic "Advantages and disadvantages of watching TV?". The discussion was conducted on the basis of three small texts in which schoolchildren express their point of view about the harm and benefits of television. Three advanced pupils represented the opinion of these pupils, the rest asked questions. Next technique is named as Onion. Pupils

of two groups form two circles (one inside the other) and turn to face each other. For some time, they discuss the question proposed by the teacher or ask questions and get answers. At the signal of the teacher, the pupils of the outer circle move to the right, thus a new pair is formed in which the discussion takes place. This form of work is effective when training any grammatical structure.

Overall, having studied the use of innovative technologies in learning a foreign language as a problem of methodology, we came to the conclusion about the insufficient effectiveness of the use of innovations. The reasons for this are that, firstly, the haste to introduce innovations leads to the fact that the innovation is forgotten or canceled by order.

References

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